

Towards a methodology for monitoring and evaluating living labs: Insights from the early stages within the SCORE Project

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Abstract

Monitoring and evaluation is a recognized method to achieve the intended results and examine the outcomes and impacts of a given intervention. In this study, we propose and apply a framework of key themes, indicators, and corresponding data collection methods for monitoring and evaluating living labs. The framework is applied in ten “Coastal City Living Labs” which are part of the Smart Control of the Climate Resilience in European Coastal Cities (SCORE) project. Ultimately, the comparison of applying the framework across ten different cases is assessed with the aim of generating a universally applicable framework for M&E of LLs.

Key words

Living labs, monitoring, evaluation, methodology, impact, sustainability

Introduction

Monitoring and evaluation (M&E) is a recognized method to achieve the intended results and examine the outcomes and impacts of a given intervention (Myrick, 2013). More specifically, M&E assesses (1) whether the intended results are being delivered to the stakeholders; (2) how these results are being achieved over time; and (3) the actual outcomes and impacts of the intervention. When implemented consistently, M&E allows for learning and change over time (Masuku et al., 2015). The participatory aspect in the M&E is especially relevant for Urban Living Labs (ULLs) where co-creation among a variety of stakeholders is used to address complex (urban) challenges (Menny, 2018). Chronéer et al. (2019, p. 60) define ULL as a “a local place for innovative solutions that aims to solve urban challenges and contribute to long-term sustainability by actively and openly co-constructing solutions with citizens and other stakeholders”.

Although M&E is a core element of ULLs, few frameworks have been developed or applied. There is a need for a universally agreed upon strategy on how to measure and evaluate the performance of a given process within the LL, especially concerning its wider impacts (Bronson et al., 2021; Ballon et al., 2018). In this context, Ståhlbröst, et al. (2012) suggest five elements to assess impact. However, Ståhlbröst, et al. (2012) 's framework represents an evaluation of the LL after activities have started or even finished. M&E is beneficial for a ULL from an early stage on. A pre-evaluation of the setup phase provides a baseline for the assessment of the ULL overall performance over time (Ravetz, et al., 2018). M&E is also relevant for assessing the LLs in the interim for reflection, learning, and continuous improvement. In this way, necessary interventions can be introduced during the process.

Furthermore, in Ståhlbröst, et al. (2012)'s framework, insights on how the indicators should be operationalised or assessed have not been provided. In that regard, Mastelic, et al. (2019) propose a set of key performance indicators (KPIs) for the assessment of LLs which consider funding structures, target audiences, and revenue streams among other important factors that need to be assessed continuously over time by different stakeholders. Such academic contributions show the scientific relevance for further developing these frameworks for LLs and synthesizing previous findings into an easily applicable methodology for practitioners. On the other hand, there is practical relevance for these frameworks, considering the proliferation of LLs across varying geographical locations and thematic sectors.

From a societal perspective, the European Union (EU) puts a strong focus on citizen

participation in the design and implementation process of innovation projects from different research areas to boost democracy and legitimacy of interventions. Horizon 2020 is an example of such as programme, where the use of LLs is specifically promoted (European Commission, 2013), for example, in the field of adaptation to climate change. To better assess the overall impact of the LL concept across different projects and disciplines, a uniform framework would be highly beneficial.

By applying the same framework in each LL from each project within the Horizon 2020 programme, cross-project comparisons would be more viable, which could enable an overall assessment of the contextual scope in which LLs are most effective and impactful. Moreover, as participants often have limited experience with the LL concept and methodology, a baseline and interim assessment could provide guidance in the setup of the LL. Outside of EU funded projects, such a framework could also enable a broader adoption of ULLs as a support tool for a more structured implementation of LLs. However, there is no uniform framework for a baseline and interim assessment of ULLs in scientific literature and an overall lack of strategies and contributions in that context.

In this study, we outline a framework of key themes, indicators, and corresponding data collection methods for M&E of ULLs. For this purpose, we rely on existing M&E frameworks and methods for LLs as well as general principles of M&E. The framework is applied in ten (10) “Coastal City Living Labs” (CCLLs) which are part of the SCORE: Smart Control of the Climate Resilience in European Coastal Cities project. Ultimately, the comparison of applying the framework across ten different CCLLs - and its assessment - can support the development of a universally applicable framework for M&E of LLS.

Methodology

The methodological approach consists of four steps. First, a literature review was conducted to identify criteria clusters and key indicators for the M&E of the CCLLs. Second, these were reviewed and validated by different groups, which resulted in deriving ten (10) criteria clusters for the M&E of ULLs. Third, data were collected through survey questionnaires, complemented by online meetings with all 10 CCLLs. These 10 CCLLs are as follows: Sligo and Dublin in Ireland; Oeiras, Portugal; Gdansk, Poland; Piran, Slovenia; Samsun, Turkey; Massa, Italy; and Benidorm, Oarsoaldea, Basque Country; and Vilanova I la Geltru / Barcelona Province in Spain. Fourth, a qualitative analysis that compared the outcomes of applying the framework across all

10 CCLLs have been conducted.

Literature review

The literature review yielded 14 different frameworks for LLs (See Table 1 in Annex). The indicator clusters included themes such as results, tools, solutions, resources, participants, intellectual property rights, operations, activities, communication, organisation, processes, and knowledge sharing/learning. These clusters included a total of 80 indicators which track the progress of the CCLLs. The indicators were divided into baseline assessment, interim assessment, and impact assessment.

Validation

Once the list of criteria clusters and respective key indicators was finished, we validated the strategy internally, externally and with the CCLLs. Firstly, an internal review of the strategy was performed by 14 members of the SCORE project. Secondly, an external review via a public webinar was performed. Thirdly, validation of the LL M&E strategy happened through the online meetings with the CCLLs.

Resulting from the literature review and the three-step validation process, an overview of the major themes, including the corresponding key indicators, for the baseline and interim assessment of CCLLs has been prepared. See Tables 2 and 3 in Annex for the overview of the major themes and key indicators for baseline and interim assessment.

By interim assessment, we refer to the phases of the living lab integrative process adopted for SCORE: Phase 1: Empathise and define; Phase 2: Ideate and co-design; Phase 3: Prototype and pilot; and Phase 4: Test and evaluate. In this document, we first focus on Phase 1: Empathise and define. As for the impact assessment, the main themes and key indicators will still be finalized with the CCLLs.

Data Collection

Data was collected through survey questionnaires, complemented by online meetings with CCLLs. These questionnaires were answered by team members from each CCLL for the baseline assessment in the following periods: January 2021 and April - May 2022. For the interim assessment, CCLL team members and stakeholders provided their responses via questionnaires in April - May 2022 and December 2022 for Phase 1: Empathise and define.

See Tables 4 and 5 in Annex for the survey questionnaires.

Data Analysis

A comparative analysis is suitable for small to intermediate numbers of cases, aiming at a systemic cross case comparison while maintaining case sensitivity. The cases were selected through literal replication, meaning that the selection processes focused on a similarity of the setting in each case. Although the ten CCLs vary in their geographic, economic, and demographic features, they are all coastal cities, part of the SCORE project, and in the process of implementing a CCLL. A qualitative analysis comparing the outcomes of applying the framework is in progress.

Preliminary Results and Conclusions

Few frameworks have been developed or applied for monitoring and evaluating LLs. There is then a need for a universally agreed upon strategy on how to measure and evaluate the performance of a given process within LLs, especially concerning its wider impacts (Bronson et al., 2021; Ballon et al., 2018). Further, M&E is beneficial for LLs from an early stage on, starting with a pre-evaluation of the setup phase as a baseline for the assessment of the overall performance (Ravetz et al., 2018). In this study, we propose and apply a framework of key themes, indicators, and corresponding data collection methods for M&E.

For this purpose, we relied on existing M&E frameworks for LLs as well as general principles of M&E and from the review and feedback from multiple groups which resulted in 10 criteria clusters. The M&E framework is applied in ten CCLs which are part of the SCORE project. Preliminary data were collected through survey questionnaires, complemented by online meetings with the 10 CCLs. A qualitative analysis comparing the outcomes of applying the framework is in progress. Ultimately, the comparison of applying the framework across ten different cases is assessed with the aim of generating a universally applicable framework for M&E of LLs. This addresses the need for frameworks and methods for M&E and for LLs to monitor their progress and performance over time.

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